

The Influence of Make a Match Type Cooperative Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 2 about the Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in Class V Students of UPTD SD 124385 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

The background to this research is based on observations made by researchers in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar, namely that teachers still use conventional learning models, resulting in low student learning outcomes. From the problems described above, it is necessary to find a solution, namely by implementing the Make a Match type cooperative learning model. This model is suitable for use in all subjects and this model is suitable for use in class V because this learning model invites students to work together and trains students' courage to appear in front of the class so that student learning outcomes can improve. This research used a pre-experimental method with a one group pretest-posttest design with a sample of 25 students. Based on the results of the data analysis test used, the Hypothesis Test results obtained were $T_{count} = 17.321$ and $T_{table} = 2.064$ with $T_{count} > T_{table} = 17.321 > 2.064$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. With this explanation, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Make a Match Type Cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

Quality education will have a big impact on everyday life and produce superior people for national development. Manurut Kusuma and Khoirunnisa (2018:1). Education is a process that contains many aspects that are interrelated and dependent on one another. Apart from that, education is a conscious effort to prepare students through guidance, teaching and training activities for their roles in the future. In general, education is a process using certain methods, so that people can gain knowledge, understanding and ways of behaving according to their needs. Education can also be translated as stages of development of human abilities and behavior, as well as the process of using all life experiences.

Learning is a process or effort carried out by each individual to obtain changes in behavior, both in the form of knowledge, skills, attitudes and positive values as an experience from various material that has been studied.

Meanwhile, learning is the main determinant of educational success. Learning is a system, which consists of various components that are interconnected with each other. These components include: objectives, materials, models, methods, strategies and evaluation. These five components will be used in learning. In essence, learning is a process of interaction between teachers and students, both direct interaction, such as face-to-face activities, and online, namely by using various learning models and media. In learning, teachers must be able to create conducive conditions so that teaching and learning communication interactions occur between teachers, students and other components to achieve good learning goals.

The Make a Match type cooperative learning model or looking for a partner was developed by Lorna Curran in 1994. In this learning model students are invited to look for a partner while learning to use a concept or topic in a fun atmosphere. This make a match type cooperative learning model involves students directly in the learning process, so that students pay more attention and enjoy the learning process more because this technique is packaged like a game without removing the essence of the learning process. According to Wijendra (2022:9633), the Make a Match type cooperative learning model (looking for partners) is a game where players use cards containing questions and answers to questions included on other cards to find partners.

Learning outcomes or achievements are the realization or expansion of a person's potential skills or capacities. According to Hamalik (2018:38) learning outcomes are changes in a person's behavior that can be observed and measured in the form of knowledge, attitudes and skills. This change can be interpreted as an improvement and development that is better than before, from not knowing to knowing. By looking at the influence of the Make a Match type cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes, this model can be used in learning in class V elementary school. Therefore, researchers aim to determine the effect of the Make a Match type cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

In carrying out research activities, the theoretical framework contains theories related to the research title regarding Theme 2 Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in class V. Students are expected to be bolder in expressing their respective opinions so that students' learning outcomes become better. Good. This conceptual framework can be depicted in the concept map below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this research is experimentation with a quantitative approach. Arikunto (2018:9) states that experimentation is one of the methods used to look for a causal relationship (casual relationship) between two factors that are deliberately created by researchers by eliminating or reducing other disturbing factors. The type of research carried out was the Pre-Experimental Design method, with a research design using a One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design. The population in this research is all class V students consisting of 25 students in one class and the sample for this research is 25 students. The instrument in this research is a test instrument. The instruments in this research were test questions that were tested using validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differential power tests. Other data is collected through documentation results. Then the data results were analyzed using hypothesis testing using the paired samples test analysis technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was carried out in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year from 2 to 14 October 2023. The population used in this research was all students in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar with a research sample of 25 students. This research aims to determine the effect of the make a match type cooperative learning model on the learning outcomes of class V students in Theme 2 Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in lesson 5 where in lesson 5 there are 3 main learning contents, namely: Science, Indonesian, SBdP. The number of students in this study was 25 students. However, before researchers conduct research, researchers test the test instrument first.

Where the instrument test was carried out in the same class but at a different school and the number of questions given to students was 30 questions. This instrument test was carried out at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar. From the instrument test carried out by the researcher, results were obtained where of the 30 questions tested, there were 25 questions that were included in the valid category and 5 questions that were invalid. So these 25 valid questions are what the researchers will give to schools that will be studied using pretest and posttest. Based on the pretest results, the average score for student learning outcomes is 62.4. And 20 students got scores below the KKM and 5 students got scores above the KKM. Looking at the average percentage of students' pretest scores, it can be said that student learning outcomes before using the Make a Match Type Cooperative learning model were still relatively low.

After the researcher carried out a normality test in the form of a pretest. Meanwhile, the average score for student learning outcomes during the posttest or after being treated using the Make a Match type cooperative learning model was 82.4, where all 25 students scored above the KKM. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, there is a value of $T_{count} > T_{table}$, namely $17.321 > 2.064$ or significant $0.00 > 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an influence of the Make a Match Type Cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in Class V UPTD of SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

Table 1. T Test Result

		Paired Differences					T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Posttest - Pretest	20,000	5,774	1,155	17,617	22,383	17,321	24	0,000

Based on table 1 above, the results of the t test, hypothesis testing which was carried out to determine whether or not there was an influence of the Make a Match Type Cooperative Learning Model on student learning outcomes in

Theme 2 Subtheme 2 Class V, carried out a t test with the help of SPSS 21 and obtained a T count of 17.321. Based on the T table of $df\ n-1 = 24$ at a significance level of 0.05, the T table value is 2.064. The results show that the value of $Tcount > Ttable$ is $17.321 > 2.064$ or significant $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So "There is an influence of the Make a Match type cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 2, subtheme 2, the importance of clean air for breathing, lesson 5 in class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar." This is done using the t test, in other words the hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion of the results of this research, it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of class V students in the Pretest and Posttest were very influential after the students received the Make a Match Type Cooperative learning model treatment. This can be seen from the average Pretest score of 62.4. And the average score from the Posttest is 82.4. The results of hypothesis testing on the Paired Sample T-Test with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and Ttable of 2.064 with a Tcount of 17.321. Thus $Tcount > Ttable$ is $17.321 > 2.064$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So from the test results it can be concluded that there are student learning outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 2 The Importance of Clean Air for Respiration in Class V UPTD SD Negeri 124385.

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